

Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI)

Educating RDM: This track is on data literacy – educating users on research data management but also for skills development in domains

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Using science reading to lay the foundation for effective reuse of scientific information:

Access to the data alone is not enough to correctly reuse it, we must understand how the data were derived

Monica Gonzalez-Marquez <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-5878-3706>

¹ Forschungszentrum Jülich, Germany

*Correspondence: Monica Gonzalez-Marquez, mg246@cornell.edu

Abstract

Research data management is committed to making research data reusable. Although there are many data repositories, a common complaint is that the vast majority of the data sets they contain are at best only partially usable as they lack key information. What has gotten lost in the conversation is that effective research data management is ultimately about the information needs of people. This means beginning by acknowledging the types of participants involved in data reuse: user and producers of research data. Both require role-specific training. Users must be trained in how to understand and interact with data sets. Producers must understand what data should be preserved and in what form. Further, optimal training for both groups requires flipping roles and seeing data from their counterpart's perspective. For users it means understanding the processes and labor involved in creating data so that it is clear what type of data archiving is and is not possible. For a producer it means understanding the information needs of users so that the data they need is made available in forms they can use most effectively. As such, the driving force of effective research data management is ensuring not only the preservation, but the usability of scientific information.

In this talk, we describe a teaching concept that sets the stage for an effective research data management mindset. We begin by introducing Science Reading [1], [6] as a methodology to help understand the science that was done, as well as possible, given available documentation. Then we introduce Literature Content Management [2] as a tool to organize the key information gathered using Science Reading. We conclude by incorporating the various methods and tools available when searching for scientific information, including papers [3], [4], [5]. Our goal is to show how an understanding of scientific knowledge from a user perspective can more productively shape how research data management is practiced.

Keywords: Open Science, Information Literacy, Data Literacy

Author contributions

Science Reading and Literature Content Management

Monica Gonzalez-Marquez: Conceptualization, methodology, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing

Methods and tools for searching of scientific information

Monika Hotze: Conceptualization, methodology, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing

Ines Schmahl: Conceptualization, methodology, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing

Competing interests

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References

- [1] M. Gonzalez-Marquez, A. Foltz, J. K. Bye, A. Fulsher. "Science Reading: How cognitive narrative can help us understand science better." Upstream. <https://upstream.force11.org/science-reading-how-cognitive-narrative-can-help-us-understand-science-better/> (29.04.2025)
- [2] J. McKenzie, M. Page, E. Mayo-Wilson, D. Moher, Y. Takwoingi. "Prisma." Welcome to the PRISMA website. <https://www.prisma-statement.org/> (29.04.2025)
- [3] Association of College & Research Libraries. "ALA American Library Association." Framework for Information Literacy for Higher Education. <https://www.ala.org/acrl/standards/ilframework> (29.04.2025)
- [4] J. McKenzie, M. Page, E. Mayo-Wilson, D. Moher, Y. Takwoingi. "Prisma." Welcome to the PRISMA website. <https://www.prisma-statement.org/> (29.04.2025)
- [5] Higgins JPT, Thomas J, Chandler J, Cumpston M, Li T, Page MJ, Welch VA (editors). *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions* version 6.5 (updated August 2024). Cochrane, 2024. Available from www.training.cochrane.org/handbook
- [6] Gonzalez-Marquez, M., Foltz, A., Bye, J. K., Fulsher, A. J., Wilde, M. (2023) What Little Red Riding Hood Can Teach Us About Reading Science. Sinding, Michael, Aura Heydenreich and Klaus Mecke, ed. *Narrative and Cognition in Literature and Science*. Berlin: De Gruyter.